

MAPPING STRAINS AND FIBRE FRACTURE IN CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES USING IN SITU DIGITAL VOLUME CORRELATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel application of Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) and *in situ* Synchrotron Radiation Computed Tomography (SRCT) to uniaxial loading in Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs). DVC is a relatively novel tool for quantifying full-field volumetric displacements and implicit strain fields [1]. To permit the application of DVC to displacements and/or strain measurements parallel to the fibre direction in well aligned unidirectional (UD) materials, a methodology was developed for the insertion of sparse populations of sub-micrometre particles within the matrix to act as displacement trackers (fiducial markers). For the novel materials systems we have developed, measurement noise is considered, along with the spatial filtering intrinsic to established DVC data processing. The evolution of individually fractured filaments into clusters of breaks is presented, together with the associated elevated strain region. A balance of spatial resolution and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is discussed in relation to measuring local micromechanical phenomena, such as ineffective length, within the bulk material. It is shown that novel, mechanistically consistent measurements may be made in relation to fibre failure events.

1 INTRODUCTION

A fundamental understanding of the fibre break process is important for a complete interpretation of composite tensile failure, alongside the various other forms of composite damage that exist. When a fibre breaks under tension, its local load transfer capability is degraded. This leads to the surrounding matrix being loaded in shear, transferring load into adjacent fibres, and back onto the broken fibre [2], [3], [4], [5], [6]. Consequently, the broken fibre recovers its stress and the length over which this process occurs is widely referred to as the ineffective length [7]. More specifically, Rosen [8] defines the ineffective length as twice the fibre length over which 90 % of strain recovery occurs. Adjacent to a broken fibre, the stress in immediately neighbouring filaments is generally recognised to increase, dependent on a distance away from the break plane (overload length), which then raises the probability of fracture in these surrounding fibres [9]. This increase in the local stress has for example been quantified by Swolfs *et al.* [10] in a T700S-based Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) using 3D Finite Element Methods (FEM). The stress concentration factor (SCF), defined as the relative change in the average stress over the cross-section of a neighbouring fibre due to the presence of a fibre break is reported to increase the probability of fracture of the neighbouring filaments [7], [9], [10], which is otherwise dominated by a Weibull distribution [11]. Therefore, the neighbouring fibres will locally carry stress concentrations, but with the magnitude decreasing with increasing distance from the fibre break [9], [10], [12], [13]. Catastrophic failure is assumed to occur when sufficient neighbouring fibres are broken, and a critical cluster is formed [9]. A significant step forward in composite damage analysis has been achieved in recent years by the use of Computed Tomography (CT) to identify detailed chronologies of damage events down to the fibre level, in 3D, within the bulk of real materials under load [14]. As a progression from this, we identify the use of Synchrotron Radiation Computed Tomography (SRCT) with Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) for a strain-based quantification of the local deformation surrounding fibre break sites. Whilst not addressed here, applications to other aspects of composite micro and meso-mechanics may be envisaged (e.g. influences of porosity or ply drops on local load paths/partitioning).

The highly anisotropic and somewhat regular microstructures found in conventional unidirectional (UD) CFRPs are intrinsically sub-optimal for DVC, particularly along the fibre direction. The cylindrical

structure of the filaments makes finding a correlation peak along the fibre direction difficult, leading to false correlation peaks along the fibres, and correspondingly inaccurate displacements in this direction within a given ply [15]. Following a similar approach to that taken by Brault *et al.* [16] to generate individual features unique to a particular sub-set, the authors have explored the insertion of sparse populations of significantly smaller (sub-micrometre) particles within the matrix to act as displacement trackers (fiducial markers). In this paper we specifically seek to address high resolution, single-fibre level processes (imaged at voxel resolution 0.65 μm), as opposed to the ply-level studies in [16] (voxel resolution 52 μm). We report on the development of the fiducial-adapted CFRP, corresponding *in situ* SRCT tensile testing, DVC processing, and exemplar micromechanical strain mapping results.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Cross-ply laminates, with a $[90/0]_s$ layup, thickness of ~ 1 mm and nominal fibre volume fraction of ~ 0.55 were manufactured by filament (drum) winding at KU Leuven, Belgium. A 12K Toray TORAYCA[®] T700SC [17] non-twisted tow was used, with 7 μm nominal fibre diameter. In order to create microstructural fiducial patterns for the application of DVC, the resin was filled with various commercially available particles (US Research Nanomaterials, Inc. [18]) of spherical geometry with a reported mean size of 400 nm. BaTiO₃ (tetragonal) was selected following extensive CT-based microstructural analysis on a range of particle compositions (Al, Al₂O₃, SiC, SiO₂, MgO, TiC, TiO₂, BaCO₃, BaTiO₃, Cu and Bi₂O₃), mean sizes (300 nm to 800 nm) and concentrations (0.25 wt. % to 15 wt. % of the resin). From the investigated set, BaTiO₃ particles were found to offer the most favourable trade-offs between contrast in the CT images (high attenuation coefficient), particle dispersion, and the ability to obtain a sufficient distribution for local DVC analyses – **Fig. 1**. The particles were stirred into a Sicomin SiPreg KTA 313/SR 8500 dual-component epoxy [19] using a combination of high-shear mixing and heated ultra-sonification. To remove entrapped air, the mixture was degassed for 10 minutes at ambient temperature. The amount of resin used was 150 g, with 31.51 g of hardener, following the manufacturer's specified mixing ratio of 100/21 (by weight). The BaTiO₃ fraction was set at 7.5 wt. % of the resin, corresponding to ~ 1.43 vol. %. A nominal 25 % tow overlap was targeted during the winding process. A maximum spool tension of 0.12 lb (54.43 g) was applied. To control the volume fraction of the matrix, following impregnation, the tow was passed through a flat die with an orifice of 0.2 mm x 9 mm. The temperature of the tow spreader and final guide roller were set to 50°C. The fibre sizing was left intact. A schematic of the manufacturing setup is shown in **Fig. 2**. The drum winding process resulted in uniaxial prepreg tape, ~ 0.25 mm in thickness and ~ 350 mm in width, which was cut and laid up to produce the desired $[90/0]_s$ layup. The prepreg stack was cured in an autoclave for 280 minutes at 0.5 MPa (5 bar) and 120°C. To mitigate void content in the cured material, a vacuum of ~ 0.07 MPa (~ 0.7 bar) was maintained throughout the autoclaving process.

Figure 1 – Lab μCT 2-D digital slice illustrating the fiducial distribution of different particle systems: (a) BaTiO₃ 400 nm, 7.5 wt. % in resin and (b) MgO 300 nm, 10 wt. % in resin

Figure 2 – Schematic illustration of the prepreg manufacturing (drum winding) process

2.2 Specimen loading and geometry

Double-edge notch specimens were extracted via water-jet cutting from the manufactured CFRP plate described in **Section 2.1**. The specimen geometry is based on previous work of Scott, Moffat, Wright, Garcea and co-workers [14], [20], [21], [22], although here the total specimen length was increased to 100 mm. The latter was performed to (a) minimize the risk of pull-out from the central 0° portion of the gauge region, and (b) to accommodate a smaller X-ray propagation distance, by providing sufficient clearance between the top of the loading rig and detector optics. Once cut, the T-shaped sections of the specimens were tabbed with 1.5 mm thick aluminium sheet. Aerospace-grade adhesive, 3M™ Scotch-Weld™ EC-9323 B/A [23], was used to bond the tabs onto the CFRP surface. Adhesive curing was performed at 65°C for 2 hrs. according to the manufacturer’s recommendations. **Fig. 3 (a)** shows the key specimen dimensions, while **Fig. 3 (b)** presents the tabbed assembly. Tensile loading was performed *in situ* by using a modified DEBEN CT5000 [24] electromechanical rig retrofitted with a Poly(Methyl Methacrylate) – PMMA reaction tube (25 mm OD and 3 mm wall thickness). Loading was performed at a displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min. Typically, ten load steps were applied for stepwise *in situ* measurements, with somewhat smaller load increments being made closer to failure. This was applied on the basis of the work of Scott *et al.* [14] where fibre breaks have been shown to follow a power law curve with the majority of events occurring above 90 % UTS. To mitigate potential effects of specimen relaxation under load (and thus potential movement during CT acquisition), scanning was carried out with a slight reduction in load ($\sim 10\%$) from the most recent peak level. A small preload (50 N) was applied for the static and rigid body displacement scans (**Section 3**) to ensure that the specimen did not move during acquisition and/or manipulator stage translation.

Figure 3 – Tensile specimens: (a) key specimen dimensions and (b) tabbed assembly (CFRP plus aluminium tabs)

2.3 Synchrotron Radiation Computed Tomography

In situ SRCT measurements were carried out at the ID19 beamline, ESRF, Grenoble, France. A detector size of 2560 x 2160 pixels was used with a chip size of 6.5 μm . Scans were conducted at a 10x magnification, yielding a voxel size of 0.650 μm and a field of view (FOV) of $\sim 1.66 \text{ mm} \times \sim 1.40 \text{ mm}$. The beam energy was set at 19 keV, with 2996 projections acquired per scan at an exposure of 25 ms, resulting in $\sim 75 \text{ s}$ per tomograph. Acquisition was performed over a rotation of 180°. A propagation distance of $\sim 30 \text{ mm}$ was used, while the data was reconstructed using conventional absorption-based Filtered Back Projection (FBP).

2.4 Digital Volume Correlation

Digital Volume Correlation was performed using the commercial DaVis 10.0.3 package (LaVision GmbH, Göttingen, Germany) [25]. The correlation process between two adjacent volumes ‘A’ and ‘B’ is illustrated schematically in **Fig. 4**. Following a transformation (affine shape function), the new position of each sub-set centroid is matched based on the distribution of grey-levels between the undeformed and deformed state [26]. The correlation coefficient measures the conservation of the grey-levels between the original and displaced sub-set, with the position determined for which the correlation is closest to unity [15]. Analogous to DIC, the correlation coefficient can be used to evaluate the similitude between the sub-sets [26]. A coefficient of 1.0 implies that the volumes are completely related, whereas a value of 0 indicates that they are completely unrelated [26].

The associated shift (3D displacement) is given by the vector connecting the sub-set centroids of initial and deformed state [25]. Finally, 3D strain field estimation may be carried out from the numerical differentiation of the displacement points [1], [27]. More information on the DVC technique can be found in Bay *et al.* [28].

Figure 4 – Schematic diagram of the DVC process. Adapted from Xu [1].

A multi-step, multi-pass strategy was adopted, whereby a global pre-shift was computed through a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) approach, followed by Direct Correlation (DC). The approach maximised the ability for the BaTiO₃ particles to be used as fiducial markers along the fibre direction, as the search for the corresponding sub-set in the deformed state was confined to a shift equal to the search radius. Furthermore, the approach allowed for the coarse displacements captured by larger sub-sets to be used as a predictor vector field for the subsequent and refined iterations, involving smaller sub-sets.

The search radius was incrementally reduced from 8 to 6 and finally 4 voxels between the deformed and undeformed state. The latter value corresponds to a typical fibre-break opening, implying that the local displacements within the microstructure cannot exceed the aforementioned amount. To achieve a high degree of sampling, the overlap between the neighbouring sub-sets was set to 75 %. This represents a higher sampling rate than that previously reported by Borstnar *et al.* [15] and Gillard *et al.* [26], where a 50 % sub-set overlap was used. Correlation was carried out relative-to-first, implying that each volume

was correlated with the first from the series, *i.e.* the initial static scan. **Table 1** presents the settings used in detail.

Final isotropic sub-set size (voxels)	FFT pre-shift (voxels)	Step 1 (voxels)	Step 2 (voxels)	Step 3 (voxels)	No. of passes steps 1-3	Voxel binning step 1	Voxel binning step 2	Voxel binning step 3
32	64	64	40	32	2	4x4x4	2x2x2	NONE
40	80	80	48	40				
48	80	80	56	48				
52	80	80	56	52				
60	96	96	64	60				
72	128	128	88	72				
80	128	128	96	80				
100	144	144	112	100				
120	176	176	136	120				

Table 1 – Summary of DVC settings used in the multi-step, multi-pass approach. A 75 % sub-set overlap was applied.

In order to assess noise and sensitivity associated with the DVC technique, stationary and rigid body displacement tests were performed (**Section 3**). DVC was applied to a cropped volume from the 0° plies, measuring 600 x 600 x 600 voxels. Volumes were carefully checked in advance against the presence of major CT artefacts and/or appreciable variations in sharpness within the visible region. As summarized in **Table 2**, the number of DVC slices is computed by dividing the height of the cropped volume (600 voxels) by the step size used in the correlation algorithm. Such an example is illustrated in **Fig. 5**. Finally, as reported by Borstnar *et al.* [15], a 32-bit floating point to 8-bit integer conversion was performed to lower the correlation time. Buljac *et al.* [29] has shown that such rescaling has negligible impact on the DVC error.

Sub-set size (voxels)	Step size (voxels)	No. of DVC slices (Z-direction)	No. of raw data slices per DVC slice
32 x 32 x 32	8	75	8
52 x 52 x 52	13	46	13
60 x 60 x 60	15	40	15
72 x 72 x 72	18	33	18

Table 2 – Number of DVC slices for a given sub-set size with 75 % overlap and corresponding number of raw data slices per DVC slice. Smaller sub-set size (and step size) infers better sampling (less averaging), but higher strain errors.

Figure 5 – Stack comprising of 33 DVC slices in the Z-direction, applicable for a sub-set size of 72 voxels with 75 % overlap. Each DVC slice is representative for 18 raw data slices. Raw data volume: 600 x 600 x 600 voxels. Y-axis indicates the fibre and loading direction respectively. X-axis is orthogonal to the fibre direction.

A common post-processing element to strain computation via DVC (and related DIC algorithms) is the Virtual Strain Gauge (VSG) [27]. The VSG defines the local region of the image that is used for strain calculation at a specific location, and may be considered to be a smoothing/denoising strategy. More details about the application of the VSG can be found in [27]. In this paper, a VSG with a strain window of 3 x 3 x 3 data points (sub-sets) was initially used for volumetric strain computation.

3 NOISE AND SENSITIVITY

To evaluate the metrological performance of the DVC technique, noise studies were conducted. The assessment involves two studies, with the approach being similar to that of Borstnar *et al.* [15], Gillard *et al.* [26] and Pierron *et al.* [30]. The first is a stationary analysis, which involves repeated scanning of the same specimen without any alterations in load (zero displacement, zero strain) or CT parameters (exposure, number of projections, beam energy, current or propagation distance). The purpose of this static noise test (SNT) is to quantify the intrinsic scanning noise and bias. The second study is a rigid body displacement (RBD) in which the specimen was moved *in situ* by a predefined displacement, parallel to the fibre direction (Y-axis), using the manipulator stage. CT acquisition was performed between each specimen position to evaluate the magnitude of the displacement vector fields and to assess any interpolation and/or system errors associated with the DVC approach [15].

3.1 Static Noise Test

Under ideal conditions, the obtained displacement vector data and implicit computed strain, should be equal to zero. Noise arising from the imaging system (e.g. photon counting statistics, electrical noise, scattered radiation) and surrounding environment (e.g. induced vibrations) implies that this is never the case, and consequently sub-set displacements will generate false strains within the results [15], [26]. Literature suggests slightly different approaches in evaluating the strain error (referred to as the strain resolution). One approach takes the maximum standard deviation of the strain map (plane of sub-sets) [26], [30], while another returns the standard deviation of the measured strain components within the volume [15]. Following the first approach however can result in unrepresentatively high errors, as results can be affected by very obvious and localised scanning artefacts (e.g. rings, detector ‘zingers’). In this work, the latter approach is taken for which the error is seen to form a normal distribution with a mean of \sim zero. The advantage of this approach is that both the stochastic noise in the imaging system and any biases in the correlation algorithm are captured and accounted for [15].

A factor that significantly affects the effective strain measurement resolution is the size of the sub-set (which is an indicator of spatial resolution) used in the correlation algorithm. **Fig. 6** presents a typical effect on strain resolution with varying sub-set size. As previously reported in literature by Borstnar *et al.* [15], Gillard *et al.* [26], Sutton *et al.* [31] and Liu *et al.* [32] a compromise can be observed between strain and spatial resolution. Of specific interest in this paper is the normal strain ϵ_{yy} , parallel to the fibre direction. Considering the normal strains, it can be observed that the lowest error is achieved in the fibre direction (Y), despite the fact that correlation along the fibres themselves has the lowest values, particularly in particle-free CFRPs [15]. This is expected, as the deposition of BaTiO₃ during the drum winding process occurred parallel to the fibre direction as the tow was drawn through the die; essentially creating longitudinal bands of fiducial markers which assist the correlation process significantly, eliminating the self-similar material microstructure.

The compromise between strain and spatial resolution occurs as a smaller sub-set size will contain too few unique features, in this case, the BaTiO₃ particles. In contrast, a larger sub-set will compromise spatial resolution, as the underlying deformation is representative of the average displacement of all the voxels contained within the sub-set [15]. A larger sub-set size also implies a larger characteristic length for the VSG, which in turn has a negative impact on the global length-scale over which the strains are computed.

A trade-off is identifiable in **Fig. 6** at a sub-set size of 72 voxels, where the characteristic length of the VSG measures 108 voxels. The corresponding VSG (for different sub-set sizes applied) is shown in **Fig. 7**, alongside the strain resolution (ϵ_{yy}) related to the static noise test.

Figure 6 – The influence of sub-set size on the strain resolution, illustrating the compromise between strain and spatial resolution

Figure 7 – Illustrating the trade-off between VSG and sub-set size and spatial resolution vs. strain resolution (ϵ_{yy}). Voxel size corresponds to $0.65 \mu\text{m}$.

3.2 Rigid Body Displacement

The displacement field following a movement parallel to the fibre direction was initially computed at the spatial resolution identified as a working compromise (72 voxel sub-set size, with 75 % overlap). The obtained variation in displacement is essentially negligible, with an average reading of $4.83 \mu\text{m}$ and a standard deviation of $0.00967 \mu\text{m}$. The induced Y-displacement was manually confirmed to the nearest pixel in Fiji ImageJ™ [33]. Multiple measurements were taken by determining the distance between a unique feature (e.g. a void or BaTiO₃ particle) and a reference point. The manual measurement indicates a displacement of $\sim 4.55 \pm 0.65 \mu\text{m}$, which is within the accuracy of the DVC. For smaller sub-sets, the SNT

and RBD corrected errors are collectively summarized in **Table 3**. Edge artefacts arising from volume displacements were geometrically masked prior to initiating the correlation process.

Sub-set size (voxels)	Scan Type	ϵ_{xx}	ϵ_{yy}	ϵ_{xy}	ϵ_{zz}	ϵ_{xz}	ϵ_{yz}
32	SNT	0.1178	0.0850	0.0447	0.1092	0.0828	0.0443
	RBD	0.1114	0.0885	0.0437	0.1098	0.0808	0.0429
52	SNT	0.0488	0.0320	0.0171	0.0465	0.0345	0.0170
	RBD	0.0503	0.0304	0.0165	0.0483	0.0353	0.0157
60	SNT	0.0379	0.0212	0.0125	0.0341	0.0249	0.0120
	RBD	0.0365	0.0217	0.0120	0.0342	0.0244	0.0116
72	SNT	0.0232	0.0122	0.0077	0.0205	0.0159	0.0072
	RBD	0.0242	0.0156	0.0082	0.0211	0.0158	0.0077

Table 3 – Strain resolution (%) for the SNT and RBD scans for various sub-set sizes (isotropic) with 75 % overlap. Masking applied (600 x 8 x 600) for the Y-displaced scans. Component parallel to the fibre direction (ϵ_{yy}) highlighted.

The magnitude of the RBD corrected and static strain resolutions are reasonably consistent with those reported by Borstnar *et al.* [15] in particle toughened interlayer materials. While, large rigid body displacements along the fibres are not expected to occur due to the *in situ* configuration of the experiment [15], the authors consider that compliances in the PMMA reaction tube are plausible, thereby leading to other indirect sources of specimen movement. Consequently, a conservative approach is taken here, which leads to the RBD strain resolution representing a major contribution to the experimental error.

4 STRAIN FIELD ASSESSMENT AT FIBRE BREAKS

4.1 Evolution of cluster of breaks

It is acknowledged that there can be no strains where there is no material (e.g. fibre break openings, cracks) [15]. Furthermore, correlation is not possible between ‘non-material’ at a break site, and the original material microstructure. As a key interest lies in capturing the overloading surrounding a fractured filament, a suitable approach is to create a computational domain that isolates the fibre break opening. This has been performed by the use of an algorithmic mask, based on grey-levels (LaVision GmbH [25]). The mask has been applied to each raw data slice in the deformed volumes, where all voxels with a grey-level below a threshold corresponding to the opening have been excluded from the computational domain. Therefore, the values quoted in this section refer to the average strains derived from the sub-set centroid shifts, where only voxels exceeding the aforementioned grey-levels have been incorporated. The disadvantage of this technique is that the deformation of any voids in the microstructure does not assist the correlation algorithm. Nonetheless, the impact is considered negligible due to the very dispersed distribution of voids within the CFRP.

Fig. 8 a) shows a single fibre break with an *apparent* peak strain of ~ 1.3 % on a background level of ~ 1.25 % (average across 36,000 data points) at ~ 88 % UTS. **Fig. 8 c)** presents the subsequently developed cluster of six breaks at ~ 98 % UTS, where an *apparent* peak of ~ 2.7 % is registered parallel to the fibre direction (Y). The FOV of each image from the series is $130 \mu\text{m} \times 130 \mu\text{m}$. As distance is increased radially and axially, strain levels decrease, away from the damage sites, ultimately reaching the background level of ~ 1.5 %. This trend is in line with that reported by literature [9], [10], [12], [13]. Due to the volumetric approach, this strain interaction is extended in the out-of-plane direction. **Fig. 8 d)** shows an adjacent strain map at ~ 98 % UTS with an additional fibre break (no. 7) contributing to the strain field surrounding the cluster of breaks; expected to contribute to a higher *apparent* strain concentration around breaks no. 3, 4 and 5.

Figure 8 – Evolution of a break cluster and the associated strain field: (a) applied load of 850 N, (b) applied load of 900 N, (c) applied load of 950 N, (d) neighbouring slice at an applied load of 950 N. Interpolation (smoothing) not applied to the strain map. FOV: $130\ \mu\text{m} \times 130\ \mu\text{m}$. Step size: 18 voxels. VSG: 108 voxels.

Due to the averaging effect, a key aspect of the DVC technique is that the resulting strains must be regarded as a spatially filtered representation of the real strains within the material. As such, the deformation captured is limited by the average volumetric displacement confined to a sub-set (or VSG) between the undeformed and deformed state. Remote from local discontinuities/cracks, microstructural anomalies and/or other sources of severe strain gradients, it might be expected that the isostrain assumption applies locally and the strains reported by DVC are a fair estimate both fibre and matrix deformation. Immediately adjacent to fibre breaks, this cannot be expected to hold, due to the following scenarios or combinations that can occur: (1) matrix yielding [34], [35], (2) matrix cracking in the fibre break plane [36], [37], [38], (3) fibre-matrix debonding [35], [39] and (4) dynamic effects (e.g. fibre spring-back) [2], [40], [41]. Since the break openings have been excluded from the correlation algorithm, and as the BaTiO_3 fiducial markers inscribed within the matrix are the main features used to identify correlation peaks it may be assumed that matrix deformation will dominate the DVC output. Further work will be conducted to confirm the accuracy and limitations of this hypothesis.

As the resulting strains cannot currently be isolated between a broken fibre and the surrounding matrix, computing the SCF in the neighbouring filaments represents a challenge at the current spatial resolutions. As such, a comparison against values reported in literature [9], [10], [12], [13] is not simple or direct. That is because any comparison/validation of corresponding finite element modelling must include spatial filtering (e.g. sub-set size or VSG) to match the experimental constraints. Nevertheless, a volume of increased strain surrounding a break/cluster of breaks can be computed. Key information regarding this region which encompasses the entire microstructure (*i.e.* both the fibres and matrix), can be withdrawn from **Fig. 8 c)** – in this case, from break no. 5, the background strain is reached at a distance of $\sim 80\ \mu\text{m}$ away from the break in the axial direction (Y) and $\sim 60\ \mu\text{m}$ in the radial direction. As such, the fibres inscribed within this region may be expected to experience a higher probability of failure.

4.2 Effect of spatial resolution on DVC measurements

The strain results in the longitudinal direction from the plane of two fibre breaks (doublet) are presented in **Fig. 9**. The study was repeated for an isotropic sub-set size of 32 voxels, 52 voxels, 60 voxels and 72 voxels respectively, with 75 % overlap. The 32 voxel sub-set size analysis represents a special case, where the VSG has been turned off; implying that the 3D strain field was computed by employing a central differentiation scheme, without the application of any other form of higher-order filtering. The error (RBD corrected) corresponding to the 32 voxel sub-set study, without the application of the VSG, was recalculated as 0.0928 %. For the lower spatial resolution cases, relevant errors are presented in **Section 3.2**.

Figure 9 – Strain measured in the longitudinal direction from two fibre breaks (sampled per correlation step); analysis repeated for different levels of spatial resolution. Ineffective length observed in the correlation performed with an isotropic sub-set size of 32 voxels, 75 % overlap and VSG off. Sampling is also improved with decreasing sub-set size (and implicit step size). Far-field strain sampled across all correlation steps corresponds to ~1.5 %.

From **Fig. 9** it can be observed that for the low spatial resolution cases (*i.e.* sub-set size of 52 voxels, 60 voxels and 72 voxels) the strain gradients are somewhat ‘washed-out’. More specifically, only an elevated strain length is observed with the maximum peak registering 2.46 % for the 52-voxel sub-set study – implying a higher strain than nominal, however not below the far-field value of ~1.5 %. The strain level decays as longitudinal distance is increased away from the break plane with the strain returning to the nominal state after a distance ~32 μm; measurement conditioned on the sub-set size used. As expected, the strain-elevating effect is more prominent in the 52 voxel sub-set size case, due to improved spatial resolution.

By contrast, the correlation conducted with an isotropic sub-set measuring 32 voxels (VSG off) allows for two distinct and symmetrical strain regions to be detected in the longitudinal direction, opposite to the break plane: (1) an elevated strain length measuring ~10 μm, where the recorded strain decays from a peak of ~8.76 % to the far-field level and (2) an ineffective length of ~37 μm where the strain recovers from ~0 % to the far-field level. The measurement of the elevated strain length is particularly important as together with the SCF it can increase the failure probability of the neighbouring intact filaments [7], [9]. The strain-based overload and ineffective length measurements performed here agree well with the order of magnitude reported by FEM models, albeit for a single broken fibre [7], [9], [12]. **Fig. 10** presents the results on a damage mapping illustration.

Figure 10 – Damage mapping illustration showcasing the strain field surrounding two fibre breaks. Two distinct and symmetrical regions of strains can be detected in the longitudinal direction, opposite to the break plane: (1) elevated strain length and (2) ineffective length. Arrow indicates the fibre direction (Y). The strain values (%) per correlation step are visible in white along the fibre direction. Far-field strain corresponds to $\sim 1.5\%$.

Despite the relatively short characteristic length over which the strains are averaged, this still measures $\sim 10.4\ \mu\text{m}$ (two times the sub-set centroid-to-centroid distance, or $2 \times 8\ \text{voxels} \times 0.65\ \mu\text{m}$). Subsequently, the DVC-based ineffective length and elevated strain length cannot be solely associated to a fibre ($7\ \mu\text{m}$), as the deformation encompasses the surrounding material as well. Similar to **Section 4.1**, the strains in **Fig. 9** and **Fig. 10** represent a super-positioning of all the deformations that occur within the sub-set, now however at a significantly reduced averaging length-scale. Even though the error measurement error is significantly higher, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) which is defined here as the ratio of the peak strain to the RBD corrected error, does not vary greatly – **Table 4**. The results show the importance of establishing the optimum sub-set size and implicit measurement sensitivity for the DVC results to restore the ‘true’ material behaviour.

Sub-set size (voxels)	Peak strain or signal (%)	RBD corrected error (%)	SNR
32 (NO VSG)	8.76	0.0928	94.40
52	2.46	0.0304	80.92
60	2.05	0.0217	94.47
72	1.72	0.0156	110.26

Table 4 – Summary of SNR as a function of sub-set size. RBD corrected error denotes the ϵ_{yy} normal component.

5 CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

Correlation between clusters of breaks and higher strain regions have been delineated at a level well above the measured noise. The methodology provides unprecedented opportunities to identify the local strain distributions before and after damage formation in composite materials, in three dimensions, at relatively high spatial resolutions. This in turn is expected to provide a valuable tool for developing and validating micromechanics models for composite damage and failure. Work is ongoing to compare and contrast the strain behaviour for a range of break cluster configurations, along with establishing a chronological sequence of break accumulation, from the earliest onset of damage. Owing to the 3D measurement capabilities, supplementary information is also expected to be withdrawn in relation to the

volumetric strain recovery from the plane of a break/cluster of breaks. Macro-/micro-mechanical studies will be performed to assess the performance of the fiducial-adapted material through a comparison with a conventional CFRP, of the same fibre and matrix. In terms of FEM comparison, the spatial resolution limitation is acknowledged and will be addressed in the near future by further SRCT experiments at higher magnifications and/or on an upscaled microstructure (larger filaments).

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